

Evaluation Of Performance for School Teacher Recruitment Using Mcdm Techniques With Interval Data

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 28, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Decision Makers (DMs); Parametric form of Interval Number (PIVN); Teaching performance; Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM)</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4837226</p>	<p><i>Teachers play an important role in nation building. It is the teachers who are pivotal in nurturing the children and youth of the country through education. To maintain academic standard, it is necessary to recruit teachers through an unbiased, efficient process. It is also required to evaluate teachers on a regular basis. For the recruitment of teacher in an educational institute, in this paper Parametric Form of Interval Number (PIVN) has been applied. In this paper, the recruitment of an efficient teacher involves measurement of 7 criteria and 20 sub-criteria involving imprecise, qualitative information. This paper applied PIVN with Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) methodology. The PIVN is introduced and implemented in AHP to obtain the criteria and sub-criteria weights. The different properties and arithmetic operation of PIVN are also discussed. Finally, a hybrid PIVN-TOPSIS algorithm is applied for selection of the best teacher. Comparative analysis was conducted using different MCDM techniques such as simple additive weighting (SAW), Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (WASPAS), Weighted Sum Method (WSM) to check the ranking of the teachers. Sensitivity analysis has been conducted by interchanging important criteria weights.</i></p>

Introduction

Teachers play an important role in nation building. It is the teachers who are pivotal in nurturing the children and youth of the country through education. To maintain academic standard, it is necessary to recruit teachers through an unbiased, efficient process. For the recruitment of teachers in an educational institute, a comprehensive and scientific Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) approach is required, as it involves several conflicting criteria and sub-criteria. Many a times the information required for solving the MCDM problems is often incomplete, vague, and imprecise. In teacher recruitment, many attributes have subjective evaluation where assigning a particular numeric crisp value may not be appropriate thus interval number has been used for better representation and handling of the impreciseness. Thus improved methodology capable of handling impreciseness is required and assigning weights to the criteria is of utmost priority in selecting the best alternative. It will empower various service-based institutions be it educational institutions, hospitality industry, healthcare industry and tourism industry to recruit under imprecise situations. This measure by which the service sector time and again outperforms itself is not measurable in quantifiable terms unlike the industries which deal in products. This makes it even more alluring as well as challenging to study. For instance, measuring a teacher's efficiency depends on her pedagogy of teaching, the way she interacts with students, the strategy she adopts, her knowledge base and many more variables which are unique to the teacher herself. A point estimate of subjective evaluation of performance may not be the right approach to evaluate a teacher's performance during interview. Keeping this in mind we have applied parametric form of Interval Numbers (PIVN) in multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methodologies and allotted weights to the criteria's we have identified based on our data.

There are several MCDM techniques to determine the weights. For determination of criteria and sub-criteria weights of teachers attributes, multiple DMs opinion has been incorporated in this research and their respective scaling has been aggregated by arithmetic mean method. The MCDM Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) has been used to obtain the weights. In many recruitment processes, more than one experts, more than one management representative are there who may have different priority for different attributes while recruiting teacher which leads to difference in the weightages assigned. A scientific logical approach is required to address the issue of unequal weightages assigned by different DMs. In this paper, we have used an approach which takes into consideration different weightage assigned by different DMs and ultimately gives a common weightage for final recruitment process. Proper evaluation of performance during interview is required for a better professionalism and academic growth. Evaluation and ranking helps the recruiters to identify applicants

strengths and weaknesses. Practically, it is easily understood that many attributes of a teacher are qualitative in nature and evaluation of teacher or ranking of teacher implies the conversion of qualitative attributes to quantitative by assigning proper scaling.

1.1 MCDM, fuzzy based MCDM and Interval Numbers in uncertain environment.

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was developed by the author of [1], which is a constructive technique to deal with complex decision making. As AHP works in crisp data, it fails to include the uncertainty or vagueness of the decision maker's. Thus in order to overcome this, fuzzy AHP was used where fuzzy numbers were used in comparison matrices. Fuzzy set theory was introduced by the author of reference [2]. Fuzzy sets theory deals only with the degree of acceptance but in no ways incorporate the decision maker's lack of hesitancy and insight. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFS), is an extension of Zadeh's [2] pioneering work. IFS was developed by the author of [3], is a strong tool to deal with uncertainty and vagueness. The distinct characteristic of IFS is that it ascertains each element membership degree, non-membership degree and indeterminacy degree. The author of reference [4] applied GRA form TOPSIS decision making method to find the best in supplier selection problem with interval numbers. The author of [5] utilized interval numbers in linear programming problem. The authors of reference [6] published a paper on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process is the extended version of classical AHP and fuzzy AHP to IF values for comparison matrices. The author of reference [7] proposed triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers for vendor selection using AHP. The authors of [8] introduced parametric representation of Interval numbers in functional form with arithmetic operations in symmetric, asymmetric and convex combination form. The authors of reference [9] used TOPSIS and Response Surface Method in MCDM problems with interval numbers. The authors of reference [10] proposed AHP based on TIFN to supplier selection problem. Many researchers in the recent years have worked in evaluating teaching performance in the higher institutes. The authors of reference [11] applied fuzzy set theory with the AHP and TOPSIS method to assess the performance of administration sciences Instructors. The authors of [12] proposed the extended approach of AHP and TOPSIS to RAHPTOPSIS to evaluate the accurate teaching quality in physical education in college. The authors of reference [13] explored Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) and COPRAS- method to estimate the performance level of individual teacher. The authors of [14] applied AHP and VIKOR MCDM tools to rank the 12 private universities which the ministry of education listed as a case study. The authors of reference [15] used MCDM techniques for recruitment of teacher by applying neutrosophic approach. The authors of [16] developed a structured framework used MCDM techniques in AHP and fuzzy AHP environments in the renowned engineering university of Bangladesh to evaluate the best teacher and finally TOPSIS method to rank them. The authors of [17] estimated factors and sub factor's weight by Chang's (extent analysis fuzzy AHP) and proposed fuzzy comprehensive evaluation method for teaching performance. The author of reference [18] used the combinations of AHP and SAW method to obtain the criteria weights and rank the alternative for the evaluation of lecturer performance. The authors of [19] proposed fuzzy Delphi and multi criteria study to judge and rank the English skills of pre-service teachers. The authors of [20] applied MCDM techniques to evaluate the service quality in telecommunication industry. The identification of suitable factors affecting the service quality was done using statistical tools. The weights were finally determined by fuzzy RASCH methodology. Further the selection of the service provider was evaluated using fuzzy MCDM method. The authors of reference [21] identified the best minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) using TOPSIS approach. At first response surface methodology (RSM) was used to make a correlation between machine responses and input, the non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-II (NSGA-II) was used to explore for the candidate solution. The authors of [22] used MCDM technique NTOPSIS and merged with the theory of gene expression programming (GEP), non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm-II (NSGA-II) to optimize MQL- vegetable oil synergy. The authors of [23] used parametric interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy number (PIVIFN) for the rating of the alternatives with respect to the criteria in choosing the optimal site selection. The authors of reference [24] used MCDM tools fuzzy AHP to calculate the factors and sub-factors weight responsible in choosing the best site for shopping mall construction. Finally fuzzy TOPSIS method was used in ranking the best alternative. The authors of [25-26] improvised new generalized score function of interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Further, the revised score function was discussed considering 4 counter cases. The authors of [27-28] deals with an economic manufacturing quantity (EMQ), used Euler Lagrange theory to identify the supreme product reliability and production rate in an imperfect production process. The author of [29] applied bi and multivariate analysis with graphical illustrations to observe the qualitative impact of primary and secondary level of education in higher education. To upgrade learning satisfaction in students, the author of [30] applied the concept of Kano's model in decision making. The principles and decision making diagram put forward, help the students, instructors and administrators to improve quality in teaching. The authors of [31] applied AHP methodology to select the best educational project, where the different criteria are assigned weightage by a group of DMs.

1.2 Motivation for the proposed study

There are various MCDM techniques as discussed earlier which helps in evaluating the best alternatives. As seen in the previous researches, [11-19] authors have applied different MCDM tools for evaluation of teaching performance and selecting the best. This article used Interval numbers based AHP and TOPSIS method to select the optimal alternative. Interval numbers is a conventional approach for representing the imprecise parameters. Interval numbers can be considered as an extension of triangular fuzzy number (TFN). On certain attributes, evaluation is subjective hence, instead of specific numerical value it will be more appropriate to assign an interval for awarding marks. In PIVN based approach, an interval is used instead of a single point and the evaluator will not have inconvenience about the fixed point where the degree of membership will be maximum. The TFN takes the lowest, medium and maximum values, Interval numbers unlike fuzzy numbers can be categorize into two intervals i.e., [low, medium] or [medium, high]. There are real life situation where PIVN represents the situation better than FN. For instance, Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFN) (a,b,c) where at "a" the membership starts, reaches maximum membership '1' at the point "b" then declines till 'c' where the membership becomes '0'. In real life problem of teacher recruitment, an expert may not be able to ascertain the value 'b' where the maximum membership exists for an attribute. To eliminate this hesitancy, concept of interval numbers provide a better approach to the expert. Considering an Interval Number [a, c], one can understand that throughout the interval there exists homogeneity of the information.

The aim of this research is to recruit the teachers based on an exhaustive set of attributes. The criteria's and sub-criteria's weight are calculated using PIVN- AHP methodology. Then the TOPSIS approach had been applied with PIVN to rank the Teachers.

So the concept of parametric form of interval numbers (PIVN) gives a lot of scope to decision maker in reducing the uncertainty and indeterminacy. Hardly, any research is done on PIVN- AHP and PIVN-TOPSIS, we propose this new concept so that it can help the DM's to get the appropriate alternatives in less time and easy calculations.

1.3 Novelities of the proposed study

Various research [11-19] has been done for evaluating teaching performance using different MCDM techniques all over the globe. In this article, theory related to Interval numbers in parametric form has been discussed and PIVN concepts are applied for selecting the best alternative by using AHP coupled TOPSIS with interval uncertainty.

1. Concept of interval numbers and parametric representation of interval numbers are applied to deal the uncertainties of real life MCDM problem in a better way.
2. Construction of teacher's recruitment strategy is a scientific approach. Extending the criteria and sub-criteria available in the literature, we have included all possible attributes of a teacher. Hence, criteria and sub-criteria of this research, is an extensive and exhaustive collection of attributes.
3. AHP and TOPSIS method both applied in the study with interval uncertainty.

1.4 Structure of the paper

The rest of this article is organized as follows: **section 2** consists of some definition of MCDM, concepts and arithmetic operations parametric form of interval numbers. **Section 3** describes the methodology of PIVN-AHP and PIVN-TOPSIS. **Section 4** illustrates the application of PIVN-AHP, PIVN-TOPSIS in recruitment of teachers in schools. Finally **section 5** discusses the comparative ranking obtained using different MCDM tools. **Section 6** includes the sensitivity analysis, thus the tables and graphs illustrate the different ranking. **Section 7** depicts the findings and discussions of this research. **Section 8** includes the managerial insights and future scope of this study. Finally, **section 9** covers the limitations and conclusion.

1.5 The design of the proposed research

We worked under a demo/mock set up. Under this set up, a mock interview was conducted involving seven teachers. Five DMs involving experts, teachers and management were present during the interview. Based on the performance by the applicants during mock interview the following decision matrix has been obtained.

The following diagram depicts the steps of the AHP and TOPSIS method applied for this MCDM model.

Figure 1.Flowchart for the present study

The following steps are done to solve the problem:

Step 1: The criteria and sub-criteria weights are obtained by AHP method. PIVN are used instead of crisp or fuzzy numbers.

Step 2: Decision matrix is structured to give ratings to the p^{th} alternative correspondence to sub-criteria's separately.

Step 3: TOPSIS method is applied to rank the alternatives.

2. Preliminaries

2.1 MCDM methodology for teacher's recruitment

Definition 2.1: Multi criteria decision making refers to the usage of multiple criteria's with respect to the problem, prioritizing the criteria's by assigning weights to them and finally ranking the alternatives. Criteria's can be defined as the attributes of the alternatives, the importance or preference of which is determined by the decision makers. Decision makers play an important part in MCDM, be it individual DM or a group of DMs.

2.2 Importance of the proposed research

Recruitment of efficient teacher is vital in order to meet the goals and objectives of the educational institution. The proposed research can be beneficial for the institutes and government in the following ways:

- a. It enhances the existing recruitment technique of teachers to a more quantitative method based on an exhaustive list of criteria, sub-criteria and multiple DMs.
- b. This method can be applied for the recruitment of staff and promotional ranking in different private as well as government organizations.

2.3 Concept of Interval number

Definition 1.[8] An interval number is a subset of the set of real numbers containing a closed interval of real numbers. It is represented as:

$$A = [i_L, i_R] = \{x: i_L \leq x \leq i_R, x \in \mathfrak{R}\} \quad (1)$$

Where i_L and i_R denotes the lower most and upper most value of the interval respectively and \mathfrak{R} is a set of real numbers.

2.4 Parametric Representation of Interval Number

Parametric product form considering the lower and upper values of the interval:

Definition 2.[8] Parametric Interval- valued function: let us assume an interval $[i_L, i_R]$, where $i_L, i_R > 0$. The parametric interval valued function for the interval $[i_L, i_R]$ is defined as

$$a(\delta) = i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta, \text{ where } \delta \in (0,1) \quad (2)$$

Some Results:

- a.) If $\delta = 0$, the lower value of the interval is obtained
- b.) If $\delta = 1$, the upper value of the interval is obtained

c.) For $0 < \delta < 1$, different number in between the interval is obtained.

Definition 3.[8] Let $A = [i_L, i_R]$ and $B = [j_L, j_R]$, be two interval numbers with $i_L, j_L > 0$. The interval-valued function for the interval $S = A + B$ in parametric form is given by

$$s(\delta) = i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta + j_L^{1-\delta} j_R^\delta \quad (3)$$

Definition 4.[8] Let $A = [i_L, i_R]$ and $B = [j_L, j_R]$, be two interval numbers, the interval-valued function for the interval $D = A - B$ provided $i_L - j_R > 0$ in parametric form is given by

$$d(\delta) = i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta - j_L^{1-\delta} j_R^\delta \quad (4)$$

Definition 5.[8] Let $A = [i_L, i_R]$ and $B = [j_L, j_R]$, be two interval numbers, the interval-valued function for the interval $M = A \times B$ in parametric form is given by

$$m(\delta) = i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta j_L^{1-\delta} j_R^\delta = (i_L j_L)^{1-\delta} (i_R j_R)^\delta \quad (5)$$

Definition 6.[8] Division of two Interval number: let $A = [i_L, i_R]$ and $B = [j_L, j_R]$, be two interval numbers, the interval-valued function for the interval $V = \frac{A}{B}, B \neq 0$ in parametric form is given by

$$v(\delta) = (i_L)^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta \left(\frac{1}{j_R}\right)^{(1-\delta)} \left(\frac{1}{j_L}\right)^\delta = (i_L/j_R)^{(1-\delta)} \left(\frac{i_R}{j_L}\right)^\delta \quad (6)$$

Definition 7.[8] Parametric Interval Numbers Weighted Aggregated Operator (PIVNWAO): let $\tilde{A} = (i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta)$ and $\tilde{B} = (j_L^{1-\delta} j_R^\delta)$, be two PIVN, having weight factors \hat{w}^1 and \hat{w}^2 respectively such that $\hat{w}^1 + \hat{w}^2 = 1$, then PIVNWAO is

$$\text{PIVNWAO}(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \hat{w}^1 (i_L^{1-\delta} i_R^\delta) + \hat{w}^2 (j_L^{1-\delta} j_R^\delta), \delta \in (0,1) \quad (7)$$

3 Methodology of Interval based AHP and Interval based TOPSIS

3.1 Classical AHP method

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is the mostly used MCDM tool for the evaluation of criterion weights. This method was developed by the author of [1]. It is applicable to both kind of data, be it qualitative or quantitative. AHP performs pair wise comparisons and then the priority weights are derived to specify the criteria's weight. The obtained weights lead the decision maker in choosing the best alternative. The classical AHP uses crisp values for the preference of criteria and provides crisp weights which may not reflect the impreciseness that exists. As qualitative assessment can be imprecise, in this article, the concept of interval numbers and its application to the problem of recruitment of teachers have been developed. Interval number depicts a particular range which signifies the spread of one's decision within that range.

3.2 TOPSIS method

TOPSIS method is extensively used MCDM approach in ranking the alternatives. TOPSIS was developed by the authors of [32]. TOPSIS work on the principle that the best alternative should always be closest to the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and farthest from the Negative Ideal Solution (NIS). The word 'TOPSIS' stands for Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to the Ideal Solution. The authors of [33] developed a new TOPSIS-based multi criteria approach to help decision makers in selecting the optimal alternative. The authors of [34] described the advantage of TOPSIS as follows:

- It is simple and rationale
- Good computational efficiency
- Simple mathematical tools to measure the relative performance of each alternatives

3.3 PIVN based AHP

Step 1. Construction of the comparison matrix

Generalized representation of comparison matrix in terms of Parametric form of interval number by a decision expert. As interval numbers contains infinite values rather than a crisp or exact value, they cannot be evaluated by general methods. The interval numbers are preferred here as the number which lies within the two values are also included which actually gives a lot of scope to the decision maker. Let the DMs express their judgment in the form $A_{n \times n}$ where $C_{kt} = [i_{Lkt}^{1-\delta} i_{Rkt}^\delta]$ where $k = 1, 2, \dots, m; t = 1, 2, \dots, n$ $\delta \in (0,1)$ denotes the comparative preference of criteria. In the matrix $C_{ii} = 1$ when $k = t$.

Comparison matrix of criteria in terms of PIVN for different values of δ by a single DM or a group of DMs

$$\begin{bmatrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \\ C_1 & [i_{L11}^{1-\delta} i_{R11}^\delta] & [i_{L12}^{1-\delta} i_{R12}^\delta] & \dots & [i_{L1n}^{1-\delta} i_{R1n}^\delta] \\ C_2 & [i_{L21}^{1-\delta} i_{R21}^\delta] & [i_{L22}^{1-\delta} i_{R22}^\delta] & \dots & [i_{L2n}^{1-\delta} i_{R2n}^\delta] \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ C_n & [i_{Ln1}^{1-\delta} i_{Rn1}^\delta] & [i_{Ln2}^{1-\delta} i_{Rn2}^\delta] & \dots & [i_{Lnn}^{1-\delta} i_{Rnn}^\delta] \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 2. Crispification of PIVN $\forall \delta \in (0,1)$

Step 3. Normalize each element of the Crispified matrix

$$N_{kt} = \frac{h_{kt}}{\sum_{k=1}^n h_{kt}}, \text{ where } k = 1, 2, \dots, n; t = 1, 2, \dots, n; (8)$$

Step 4. Estimation of criteria and sub-criteria weights

$$E = \frac{N^{th} \text{ root value}}{\sum N^{th} \text{ root}} (9)$$

Step 5. Checking the Consistency Index (C.I) of the matrix

$$(C.I) = \frac{\mu_{max} - n}{n-1}, (10)$$

Where n is the size of the matrix.

Step 6. The same procedure follows for the sub-criteria's and finally the global weights are obtained by multiplying the criteria's weight with the respective sub-criteria's weight.

3.4 PIVN based TOPSIS

Step 1. Formation of the decision matrix

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{11}^c & \Omega_{12}^c & \dots & \Omega_{1m}^c & \Omega_{21}^c & \Omega_{22}^c & \dots & \Omega_{2f}^c & \dots & \Omega_{n1}^c & \Omega_{n2}^c & \dots & \Omega_{nq}^c \\ T_1 & x_{111}^u & x_{112}^u & \dots & x_{11m}^u & x_{121}^u & x_{122}^u & \dots & x_{12f}^u & \dots & x_{1n1}^u & x_{1n2}^u & \dots & x_{1nq}^u \\ T_2 & x_{211}^u & x_{212}^u & \dots & x_{21m}^u & x_{221}^u & x_{222}^u & \dots & x_{22f}^u & \dots & x_{2n1}^u & x_{2n2}^u & \dots & x_{2nq}^u \\ \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots \\ T_p & x_{p11}^u & x_{p12}^u & \dots & x_{p1m}^u & x_{p21}^u & x_{p22}^u & \dots & x_{prf}^u & \dots & x_{pn1}^u & x_{pn2}^u & \dots & x_{pnq}^u \end{bmatrix}$$

Where:

i.) $\Omega_{11}^c, \Omega_{12}^c, \dots, \Omega_{1m}^c, \Omega_{21}^c, \Omega_{22}^c, \dots, \Omega_{2f}^c, \dots, \Omega_{n1}^c, \Omega_{n2}^c, \dots, \Omega_{nq}^c$ are the sub-criteria for which the alternative T_i performance is measured.

ii.) T_1, T_2, \dots, T_p are the alternatives, whose rankings are to be evaluated.

iii.) x_{ijk}^u is the PIVN of the alternative T_i with respect to the sub-criteria C_{jk} by the u^{th} decision maker.

Step 2. Normalization of the decision matrix

$$N_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n; (11)$$

Step 3. Determination of the weighted normalized matrix

$$V_{ij} = w_j \times N_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n; (12)$$

Step 4. Finding out the Positive Ideal Solution (P_{IS})A + and the Negative Ideal Solution (N_{IS})A –

$$P_{IS} = \begin{cases} \max_i (V_{ij}), (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \text{ for benefit criteria} \\ \min_i (V_{ij}), (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \text{ for non – benefit criteria} \end{cases} \\ N_{IS} = \begin{cases} \min_i (V_{ij}), (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \text{ for benefit criteria} \\ \max_i (V_{ij}), (j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \text{ for non – benefit criteria} \end{cases} (13)$$

Step 5. Calculation of the distance between alternative T_i and the Positive Ideal Solution (P_{IS})A +

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - A_j^+)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m (14)$$

Step 7. Calculating of the distance between alternative T_i and the Negative Ideal Solution (N_{IS})A –

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (V_{ij} - A_j^-)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m (15)$$

Where D_i^+ and D_i^- denotes the distance between the i th alternative from the positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution respectively.

Step 8. Calculation of the relative closeness of each alternative to the ideal solution.

$$R_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^- + D_i^+} (16)$$

4. Application of PIVN AHP and TOPSIS in Recruitment of Teaching Performance

The table 1 represents the criteria and sub-criteria of teachers [11-19] used for recruitment and subsequent ranking.

Table 1.Criteria and sub-criteria for teacher's recruitment [11-19]

Criteria	Sub- criteria
Personality (P)	Flexibility (P ₁) Classroom Management (P ₂) Kindness (P ₃)
Discipline (D)	Punctuality (D ₁) Dedication (D ₂) Well organized (D ₃)
Motivator (M)	Overall development of students (M ₁) Good Counseling (M ₂) Positive Impact (M ₃)
Communication (C)	Speaking skills (C ₁) Good listener (C ₂) Clear idea (C ₃)
Subject Knowledge (SK)	Teaching well- structured topics (S ₁) Accurate information and new ideas (S ₂) Effective Questioning (S ₃)
Professionalism (Pr)	Work Ethics (Pr ₁) Concept of confidentiality (Pr ₂)
Utilization of Technology (UT)	PPT presentation (UT ₁) Knowledge of online teaching Using ICT (UT ₂)

The following figure 2 represents the hierarchical structure of the study.

Figure 2. Hierarchical Structure representing the application
 The table 2 represents the linguistic terms in PIVN for comparing criteria and sub-criteria.
Table 2. Linguistic term in PIVN for obtaining criteria and sub-criteria weights.

Linguistic Variable	PIVN
Tremendously Important (T)	$(4^{1-\delta} 5^\delta)$
Very Strongly Important (V)	$(3^{1-\delta} 4^\delta)$
Strongly Important (S)	$(2^{1-\delta} 3^\delta)$
Fairly Important (F)	$(1^{1-\delta} 2^\delta)$
Equally Important (E)	1

Step 1. Obtaining PIVN values for different 'δ'.
 The table 3 mentioned below represents different values of 'δ'

Table 3. PIVN values for different 'δ'

Linguistic Variable	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
Equally Important(E)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Fairly Important(F)	1	1.071773463	1.148698355	1.231144413	1.319507911	1.414213562	1.515716567
Strongly Important(S)	2	2.082759488	2.168943542	2.258693871	2.352158045	2.449489743	2.550849001
Very Strongly Important(V)	3	3.087558027	3.177671523	3.270415073	3.365865436	3.464101615	3.565204916
Tremendously Important (T)	4	4.09026073	4.18255821	4.2769384	4.373448296	4.472135955	4.573050519
1/F	0.5	0.535886731	0.574349177	0.615572207	0.659753955	0.707106781	0.757858283
1/S	0.33	0.344000874	0.358595762	0.373809866	0.389669456	0.40620192	0.423435805
1/V	0.25	0.257038041	0.264274217	0.271714108	0.279363447	0.287228132	0.295314225
1/T	0.2	0.204513037	0.209127911	0.21384692	0.218672415	0.223606798	0.228652526

Step 2. Formation of comparison matrix by the linguistic term used by DM for different criteria and sub-criteria.

The following table 4 denotes the comparison of different criteria in linguistic terms obtained by DM.

Table 4. Pairwise Comparison Matrix of criteria in linguistic term

Criteria	Personality (P)	Discipline (D)	Motivator (M)	Communication (C)	Subject Knowledge (SK)	Professionalism (Pr)	Utilization of Technology (UT)
Personality (P)	E	1/V	V	1/F	1/S	S	T
Discipline (D)	V	E	S	1/F	1/S	1/F	V
Motivator (M)	1/V	1/S	E	F	1/V	1/S	S
Communication (C)	F	F	1/F	E	1/T	1/S	S
Subject Knowledge (SK)	S	S	V	T	E	S	T
Professionalism (Pr)	1/S	F	S	S	1/S	E	S
Utilization of Technology (UT)	1/T	1/V	1/S	1/S	1/T	1/S	E

Step 3. In similar manner, four decision matrix are obtained by the other DMs in linguistic terms.

Step 4. Conversion of linguistic terms to a ' δ ' value decided by decision expert. The assigned ' δ ' values by different DMs has been aggregated by arithmetic mean method.

Step 5. Normalization of the matrix using (8)

Step 6. Determination of priority weights of criteria using (9)

Table 5 represents the criteria weights obtained by PIVN-AHP methodology.

Table 5. Representation of criteria weights

Criteria	P	D	M	C	SK	Pr	UT
Weights W_i	0.1428342	0.1587953	0.0788484	0.105311901	0.323115804	0.146532333	0.044562066

From the above table 5, it is seen that the criteria 'SK' scores the maximum weight of 0.323 (rounding off) followed by 'D', 'Pr', 'P', 'C', 'M' and 'UT'.

In the similar way, sub-criteria matrices are constructed and respective weights are obtained. Finally the global weights are obtained by the product of criteria weight with their respective sub-criteria weight.

Table 6 denotes the criteria, sub-criteria and global weights which are further required for ranking the teachers taken in this study.

Table 6. Global weights representation

Criteria Weights	Sub-Criteria Weights	Global Weights
$W_1 = 0.143$	$W_{11} = 0.22$	$W_{11} = 0.032$
	$W_{12} = 0.56$	$W_{12} = 0.08$
	$W_{13} = 0.22$	$W_{13} = 0.032$
$W_2 = 0.158$	$W_{21} = 0.21$	$W_{21} = 0.03$
	$W_{22} = 0.382$	$W_{22} = 0.06$
	$W_{23} = 0.41$	$W_{23} = 0.06$
$W_3 = 0.079$	$W_{31} = 0.654$	$W_{31} = 0.05$
	$W_{32} = 0.20$	$W_{32} = 0.02$
	$W_{33} = 0.146$	$W_{33} = 0.011$
$W_4 = 0.105$	$W_{41} = 0.234$	$W_{41} = 0.02$
	$W_{42} = 0.12$	$W_{42} = 0.013$
	$W_{43} = 0.65$	$W_{43} = 0.07$
$W_5 = 0.323$	$W_{51} = 0.32$	$W_{51} = 0.10$
	$W_{52} = 0.474$	$W_{52} = 0.15$
	$W_{53} = 0.207$	$W_{53} = 0.07$
$W_6 = 0.146$	$W_{61} = 0.586$	$W_{61} = 0.08$
	$W_{62} = 0.414$	$W_{62} = 0.06$
$W_7 = 0.044$	$W_{71} = 0.22$	$W_{71} = 0.01$
	$W_{72} = 0.78$	$W_{72} = 0.03$

4.2 PIVN- TOPSIS method for selection of the best alternative.

Proposed Methodology: In this approach, for ranking of alternatives, PIVN is used to represent the numerical grading of the alternatives with respect to the criteria. The DMs considered in this study are group of 3 administrative officers $o = \{1, 2, \dots, \gamma\}$ and 2 external experts $v = \{1, 2, \dots, \rho\}$.

The individual DM gives the preference grades and then aggregation of individual groups are done by Arithmetic Mean Method. This method is more appropriate as it enables the DMs to grade the alternatives corresponding to the criteria flexibly. The ranking of alternatives is done using the sub-criteria weight.

4.3 Numerical Study

The following table 7 represents the linguistic preference of DMs in terms of PIVN.

Table 7. Linguistic variables in terms of PIVN for preferential rating of the teachers

Linguistic Variable	PIVN
Excellent	$(7^{1-\delta} 8^\delta)$
Good	$(6^{1-\delta} 7^\delta)$
Fair	$(5^{1-\delta} 6^\delta)$
Poor	$(4^{1-\delta} 5^\delta)$
Very Poor	$(3^{1-\delta} 4^\delta)$

Note 1. The different PIVN values for the TOPSIS methodology are obtained for different ' δ ' in the similar procedure as in table 2. DMs are there to rate the alternatives with respect to the sub-criteria. Their aggregation is used to determine the final decision matrix in table 8. The ' δ ' chosen by the DMs are completely based on their expertise.

Step 1. Formation of decision matrix using table 8.

Table 8 denotes the decision matrix obtained by different DMs

Table 8. The aggregated decision matrix obtained by DMs using PIVN. The linguistic terms for different PIVN are decided by DMs from table 7.

Aggregation by DMs	(P)			(D)			(M)			(C)			(SK)			(Pr)
	(P ₁)	(P ₂)	(P ₃)	(D ₁)	(D ₂)	(D ₃)	(M ₁)	(M ₂)	(M ₃)	(C ₁)	(C ₂)	(C ₃)	(S ₁)	(S ₂)	(S ₃)	
Teachers																
T ₁	4.457	4.457	4.054	2.43	2.838	2.229	3.851	4.056	3.854	3.854	3.247	4.256	3.854	3.653	4.056	3.24
T ₂	4.457	4.256	4.056	2.843	3.448	2.636	4.056	4.054	3.854	4.055	3.653	4.458	4.055	4.056	3.854	3.65
T ₃	3.854	3.248	3.45	2.637	2.637	2.229	3.45	3.854	3.248	3.854	3.854	4.457	4.056	4.056	4.056	3.65
T ₄	2.844	3.046	3.248	3.248	3.047	2.229	2.639	2.224	2.023	2.844	3.044	2.641	3.045	3.045	2.023	3.04
T ₅	3.854	3.653	2.844	4.659	3.653	2.844	2.844	3.248	2.229	3.653	3.047	3.653	3.653	3.854	2.844	3.65
T ₆	2.838	3.246	3.451	4.055	3.45	2.844	2.432	2.837	2.229	2.842	2.641	2.838	3.248	3.248	2.432	3.4
T ₇	3.046	3.249	3.248	3.046	3.046	2.025	2.43	1.82	1.82	2.434	3.041	2.637	3.248	2.637	2.229	2.84

Step 2. Calculation of normalized matrix using (11)

Table 9 denotes the normalized decision matrix.

Table 9. Computation of normalized decision matrix using (11)

Teachers	(P)			(D)			(M)			(C)			(SK)			(Pr)	
	(P ₁)	(P ₂)	(P ₃)	(D ₁)	(D ₂)	(D ₃)	(M ₁)	(M ₂)	(M ₃)	(C ₁)	(C ₂)	(C ₃)	(S ₁)	(S ₂)	(S ₃)	(Pr ₁)	(Pr ₂)
T ₁	0.458	0.464	0.437	0.274	0.338	0.343	0.46	0.47	0.508	0.427	0.379	0.441	0.403	0.39	0.482	0.363	0.4
T ₂	0.458	0.443	0.438	0.32	0.41	0.406	0.485	0.469	0.508	0.449	0.426	0.462	0.424	0.433	0.458	0.409	0.4
T ₃	0.396	0.338	0.372	0.297	0.314	0.343	0.412	0.446	0.428	0.427	0.45	0.462	0.424	0.433	0.482	0.409	0.3
T ₄	0.292	0.317	0.35	0.366	0.362	0.343	0.315	0.257	0.267	0.315	0.355	0.274	0.318	0.325	0.24	0.341	0.3
T ₅	0.396	0.38	0.307	0.524	0.434	0.438	0.34	0.376	0.294	0.404	0.355	0.378	0.382	0.411	0.338	0.409	0.4
T ₆	0.291	0.338	0.372	0.456	0.41	0.438	0.291	0.328	0.294	0.315	0.308	0.294	0.34	0.346	0.289	0.386	0.3
T ₇	0.313	0.338	0.35	0.343	0.362	0.312	0.29	0.211	0.24	0.269	0.355	0.273	0.34	0.281	0.265	0.318	0.3

Table 10 denotes the global weight of the sub-criteria used in this study.

Table 10. Representation of global weights of sub-criteria used for calculating weighted normalized matrix.

	(P ₁)	(P ₂)	(P ₃)	(D ₁)	(D ₂)	(D ₃)	(M ₁)	(M ₂)	(M ₃)	(C ₁)	(C ₂)	(C ₃)	(S ₁)	(S ₂)	(S ₃)
GW	0.032	0.08	0.032	0.033	0.061	0.065	0.052	0.016	0.011	0.025	0.012	0.068	0.103	0.153	0.067

Step 3. Estimation of weighted normalized matrix using (12)

Weighted normalized matrix of different alternatives with respect to the sub-criteria are shown in table 11.

Table 11. Weighted Normalized matrix

Teachers	(P)			(D)			(M)			(C)			(SK)		
	(P ₁)	(P ₂)	(P ₃)	(D ₁)	(D ₂)	(D ₃)	(M ₁)	(M ₂)	(M ₃)	(C ₁)	(C ₂)	(C ₃)	(S ₁)	(S ₂)	(S ₃)
T ₁	0.014	0.037	0.014	0.009	0.02	0.022	0.024	0.007	0.006	0.011	0.005	0.03	0.042	0.06	0.067
T ₂	0.014	0.035	0.014	0.011	0.025	0.026	0.025	0.007	0.006	0.011	0.005	0.032	0.044	0.066	0.067
T ₃	0.013	0.027	0.012	0.01	0.019	0.022	0.021	0.007	0.005	0.011	0.006	0.032	0.044	0.066	0.067
T ₄	0.009	0.025	0.011	0.012	0.022	0.022	0.016	0.004	0.003	0.008	0.004	0.019	0.033	0.05	0.067
T ₅	0.013	0.03	0.01	0.017	0.026	0.028	0.018	0.006	0.003	0.01	0.004	0.026	0.039	0.063	0.067
T ₆	0.009	0.027	0.012	0.015	0.025	0.028	0.015	0.005	0.003	0.008	0.004	0.02	0.035	0.053	0.067
T ₇	0.01	0.027	0.011	0.011	0.022	0.02	0.015	0.003	0.003	0.007	0.004	0.019	0.035	0.043	0.067

Step 4. To find out the $(P_{IS})A +$ and $(N_{IS})A -$ using (13)

The PIS and NIS are depicted in table 12.

Table 12. Finding out the Positive Ideal Solution $(P_{IS})A +$ and the Negative Ideal Solution $(N_{IS})A -$ using (13)

$(P_{IS})T +$	0.014	0.037	0.014	0.017	0.026	0.028	0.025	0.007	0.006	0.011	0.006	0.032	0.044	0.066	0.067
$(N_{IS})T -$	0.009	0.025	0.01	0.009	0.019	0.02	0.015	0.003	0.003	0.007	0.004	0.019	0.033	0.043	0.067

Step 5. Finding out the distance measure from the Positive ideal solution and negative ideal solution using (14) and (15) finally calculation of Relative closeness (R_i) which determines the best alternatives using (16). The maximum value of (R_i) determines the best teacher.

Table 13 denotes the distance measure of each alternative from PIS and NIS. It finally shows the ranking of the teachers.

Table 13. Representation of final ranking of teachers using PIVN-TOPSIS approach

Teachers	D_i^+	D_i^-	(R_i)	RANKING
T ₁	0.015	0.034	0.697	2
T ₂	0.008	0.039	0.832	1
T ₃	0.018	0.036	0.661	3
T ₄	0.036	0.009	0.194	6
T ₅	0.017	0.031	0.644	4
T ₆	0.03	0.017	0.371	5
T ₇	0.039	0.005	0.12	7

The relative closeness value of teacher T_2 is maximum with a value of 0.832. Thus, ' T_2 ' scores the first rank followed by the teachers ' T_1 ' scoring the second rank, ' T_3 ' third rank and so on.

$$T_2 > T_1 > T_3 > T_5 > T_6 > T_4 > T_7$$

Figure 3 represents the distance measure and ranking of individual teachers.

Figure 3.Line chart representing Distance measure i.e. $(P_{IS})A +$, $(N_{IS})A -$ and ranking i.e. (R_i) of each alternatives.

5. Comparative Analysis

Different MCDM methods such as Simple additive weighting (SAW), Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (WASPAS), Weighted Sum Method (WSM) has been applied to conduct comparative analysis. There exists high correlation between different ranking techniques. Some of them are perfectly correlated, so it shows reliability of PIVN based MCDM method which is capable of capturing minute detail regarding different attributes. SAW model was first developed by the author [35] in 1955. SAW method is popular due to its simple and easy process. SAW method is based on providing scores and mostly used in multi attribute decision making (MADM). This methodology is also known as weighted linear combination and works on weighted average. WSM is a simple and easy approach developed by the author of [36], when we deal with multiple criteria problems. WSM allows the comparison of the alternatives by giving the scores, and then these score are used to obtain the values of the alternatives which are taken for the study. WASPAS method was developed by the author of [37] in 2012. The WASPAS method is a combination of two MCDM methods WSM and weighted product model (WPM).

Table 14 depicts ranking of different teachers using MCDM methods.

Table 14. Ranking of teachers by different MCDM methods

Teachers	SAW	WSM	WASPAS(0.5)
T1	2	2	2
T2	1	1	1
T3	4	4	4
T4	6	6	6
T5	3	3	3
T6	5	5	5
T7	7	7	7

Figure 4 shows the clustered chart ranking of WASPAS, WSM and SAW methods.

Figure 4. Clustered chart representing ranking of different MCDM methods**4. Sensitivity Analysis**

In sensitivity analysis depicted in table 15 and figure 5, we obtained two more different rankings. We analyzed the most sensitive criteria and interchanged the weights. In our methodology, it was seen that the criteria 'subject knowledge' obtained the maximum weight and so its sub-criteria's. The sub-criteria 'subject knowledge' global weights were interchanged with 'personality' sub-criteria weight, thus we obtained different ranking. During COVID-19 pandemic, it is seen that online teaching skills has high importance for a teacher. During the current pandemic, it is easy to understand that how the criteria 'utilization of technology' is highly significant for learning and education at home. Thus in the second analysis, we interchanged the sub-criteria weight 'knowledge of online teaching with ICT' with sub-criteria 'accurate information and new ideas' as the later possessed maximum weight. Simultaneously the sub-criteria 'PPT presentation' weight was interchanged with the sub-criteria 'classroom management'.

Table 15. Representation of sensitivity analysis

Teachers	Ranking (Proposed Methodology)	Ranking (Interchanging Weight)	Ranking (Interchanging Weight)
T1	2	2	2
T2	1	1	1
T3	3	4	4
T4	6	6	7
T5	4	3	3
T6	5	5	5
T7	7	7	6

Figure 5. Representation of different ranking obtained under sensitivity analysis**Table 16.** Correlations between ranks obtained through different MCDM techniques

	SAW	WSM	WASPAS(0.5)	P2	P3	P1
SAW	1.000	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	.905**	.905**
WSM	1.000**	1.000	1.000**	1.000**	.905**	.905**
WASPAS(0.5)	1.000**	1.000**	1.000	1.000**	.905**	.905**
P2	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**	1.000	.905**	.905**
P3	.905**	.905**	.905**	.905**	1.000	.810*
P1	.905**	.905**	.905**	.905**	.810*	1.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

7. Findings and Discussions

It is easy to understand that factors and sub-factors are the core important for teacher's evaluation. The weights are determined by the PIVN-AHP method. It reflects that the criteria 'Subject- Knowledge' (W_5) play an important role in choosing the optimal teacher. While considering the Sub-criteria, i.e., 'overall development of students' (W_{31}) possess maximum weights.

In the proposed methodology, sub-criteria were used to perform the ranking of the alternatives. Through this approach, minute specifications can be made regarding different attributes of teaching. The teacher 'T₂' adjudged the most efficient one with a score of 0.832 whereas the teachers 'T₇' scored the least value of 0.12.

As the parameters in sub-criteria are more, this article lays more emphasis on detailed minute attributes of a teacher. Exhaustive list of sub-criteria involved in the paper ensures a holistic approach and the result is authentic, reliable. The comparative analysis showed that all the alternative ranked same using SAW, WSM, WASPAS methodology. The same ranking indicates that though the techniques are different but the preference given by the DMs for a particular alternative in different methods is consistent which helped in attaining the same ranking. The sensitivity analysis conducted in this research, showed that when the sensitive sub-criteria weights were interchanged, we obtained different ranking. The teachers 1 and 2 rankings were consistent even in interchange of weights. This proves that they excel the qualitative attributes and thus no change in their ranking.

8. Managerial Insights and future scope

It is a known fact that recruiting efficient teachers and periodic evaluation of teaching is significant in higher educational institutes (HEI). Quality teaching is expected at all the HEI. The educational administration always strives for a teacher or teachers who can upgrade the student's academic level. Thus proper teacher selection and evaluation is a continuous procedure which every colleges or Universities must conduct. This paper provides scientific approach which can be applied comprehensively to evaluate teaching performance. A scientific evaluation system is been designed to obtain the reasonable criteria and sub-criteria weights. The process can also be applied during the evaluation of teachers too. The similar methodology can be applied can be applied for best family car selection, E vehicle charging site selection, construction site selection where imprecise information is prevalent [38-45].

In future, schools can use this methodology for evaluation of teachers. In schools, teacher evaluation depends on the feedback of students. Thus a group of students can be taken additionally with the management members and experts. Weightage can be provided to individual groups depending on the importance. The weights should be assigned in such a way that $\sum \hat{w}_i = 1$.

The exact value for the decision matrix is obtained using following formula, where s, o, v represents the group of students, administrative officers and colleagues. τ used in equation 20 represents the aggregate weight.

$$s = \frac{\sum_{e=1}^{\beta} (s_{le}^{1-\delta} s_{re}^{\delta})}{\beta}, \text{ where } \delta \in [0,1] \quad (17)$$

$$o = \frac{\sum_{g=1}^{\gamma} (o_{lg}^{1-\delta} o_{rg}^{\delta})}{\gamma}, \quad (18)$$

$$v = \frac{\sum_{s=1}^{\rho} (v_{lp}^{1-\delta} v_{rp}^{\delta})}{\rho}, \quad (19)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\hat{w}_1 * s + \hat{w}_2 * o + \hat{w}_3 * v}{\hat{w}_1 + \hat{w}_2 + \hat{w}_3}, \quad (20)$$

9. Limitation and Conclusion

This paper develops AHP- TOPSIS method with the concept of parametric form of Interval Numbers (PIVN) to evaluate the teaching performance in higher institutions. Parametric form of interval numbers helped in capturing the impreciseness which arises while evaluating teaching attributes. The recruitment of teachers involves various criteria and sub criteria, so in this article the criteria and its sub-criteria weights are computed using PIVN-AHP method and finally the ranking of the teachers are conducted using PIVN-TOPSIS approach. The method can be applied to multiple organizations where several factors are responsible in choosing the right employees. For recruitment of the teachers in schools or colleges students could be incorporated in future research. Different MCDM techniques like Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluations (PROMETHEE), Vlse Kriterijska Optimizacija Kompromisno Resenje (VIKOR) can be used to rank the teachers. Different methodology such as, hesitant fuzzy numbers, generalized hesitant fuzzy numbers with MCDM tools can be used to recruit the teachers, students or employees, depending on the sector, one wants to evaluate. Since this is a behavioral science, more efficient tools may be developed in the future to capture the impreciseness in much better way. The attributes taken in this paper for recruitment of teacher may be expanded further based on recruitment criteria of the organization e.g., 'Research and Publications' should be included while recruiting professors in higher educational institutes.

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